

FAIRsFAIR project¹ comments FAIR Data Maturity Model: specification and guidelines²

The FAIRsFAIR project would like to thank the RDA FAIR Data Maturity Model WG for the opportunity to respond to this specification and guidelines. The assessment of FAIRness of individual datasets as well as the wider context of data infrastructures such as data repositories and other services is at the heart of the FAIRsFAIR project.

FAIRsFAIR partners working on FAIR Certification have actively participated in online and RDA Plenary face to face meetings organized by the WG. The project has used the output of the WG (assessment indicators v3) as a basis to develop a set of minimum metrics for assessing the FAIRness of research data objects and tools implementing those metrics to address two FAIR data assessment use cases (researchers and data repositories). FAIRsFAIR is also one of two adopters nominated by the WG as part of the RDA Recommendation Endorsement.

Below we offer general feedback to the paper and we have also provided some more detailed comments against the text.

- **Presentation** - overall the paper is well structured and clear. We would suggest that the priority level is presented alongside the detail about each indicator in addition to being shown in the overview table. We would also note that the 'RDA-' prefix makes each identifier less human-readable than in previous versions.
- **'What' and 'How' aspects of FAIR assessment** - While the indicators and their descriptions represent the 'what' aspect, the assessment details ('how') sections do not always provide sufficient detail to design a test (e.g., data type, community practices).
- **Clarity and Context** - there are a number of cases where terms are ambiguous or where more information is needed to define the contextual dependencies (e.g. community standard). FAIRsFAIR has outlined a number of these cases in the FAIR baseline text³
- **Scope and Future Work** - It is reasonable to state that the indicators have value "in the context of data-related algorithms, tools, workflows, protocols and other data-related services" but it might be useful to acknowledge that the working group scope did not include validation of all of these scenarios. See also the comment on controlled vocabularies below.
- **Open and Transparent** - To foster community-driven FAIR evaluation, the assessment details should be open and transparent by including known limitations & opportunities for further development. Potential supporting technologies and services should be described with examples.

¹ <https://www.fairsfair.eu>

² <https://doi.org/10.15497/rda00045>

³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3728131>

- **Priorities** - The priority levels may be open to interpretation, and priorities may be changed depending on context. This could impact comparison of automated test outcomes. Therefore, we should encourage the communities to consider how each indicator applies to their data/practices.
- **Evaluation method** - in contrast to 'pass/fail' the 'measuring progress' option may depend more on subjective evaluation, but both could depend on a degree of human evaluation outside of the automated tests.
- **F-indicators** - Requiring that PID be applied separately to both data and metadata may not align with the common practice where a data object is assigned with a PID and this PID resolves to a landing page that may contain the metadata of the object and the identifier (e.g., URL) to access the actual data contents. Assumptions which overgeneralise how data and metadata objects are identified in practice will influence the implementation and results of automated assessments.
- **A-indicators** - "RDA-A2-01M Metadata is guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available" could be clearly aligned with RDA-R1.2-02M to make it clear that this is a vital aspect of object provenance.
- **I-indicators** - The absence of essential indicators could be acknowledged as a potential issue for ensuring interoperability and as an area which needs further work. This is also the case for the need to define and manage FAIR-compliant vocabularies
- **R-indicators** - It is undeniable that reuse (and interoperability) are vastly improved through the use of standard licences. But to exclude all locally defined licences will impact a wide range of current data, including sensitive data or commercially negotiated data. It could also restrict the development of 'future standard' licences. We cover this in more detail in the comments.
- **Future Maintenance** - the inclusion of a section on future maintenance here is valuable. This specification and guidelines will inform a variety of assessment approaches which will in turn impact the 'reputations' of objects and the organisations which care for them. Trust in a standard is transitive so the maintenance approach should extend to the reliance on the GOFAIR text and the FAIRsharing Registry. These valuable contributions to FAIR are dependencies for future confidence in these specifications and guidelines. We provide a number of examples in our comments where a self-declared vs a managed entry in a registry will materially impact trust in the assessment process.